

ARDC Community Data Lab (CDL)

Architecture - Phase 1

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Date: 2023-02

Status: Third Draft for ARDC project team

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Overview

This document outlines a distributed software architecture for the [ARDC Community Data Lab \(CDL\)](#), formerly known as HASS Community Data Lab (HDCL).

The first phase of this project will focus on Trove as a central data source and provide extensive documentation and examples of how to process Trove and other data using existing distributed research infrastructure available to Australian researchers, including: ARDC Nectar Research Cloud (Nectar) computing services, publicly available data repositories such as Zenodo and Figshare and workspace services such as github and gitlab. This environment is a mixture of publicly funded and commercial services - some of them “free” to use (for now). We know that the mix of services will change and develop over time so this architecture is designed to be flexible and adaptable.

This is a set of high-level sketches only, that look at the functional architecture and relationships between systems, more detailed specific architectures documenting specific systems and code will form part of the deliverables for each work package.

This work builds on the [Australian Text Analytics Platform \(ATAP\)](#) project and the [GLAM Workbench](#) approach, which informed the ATAP architecture:.

ATAP is an ecosystem of tools, workspaces and repositories. At the core of the ecosystem is a portal which indexes notebooks (hosted in GitHub repositories) and data. This portal is a registry of notebooks and data, which are linked through RO-Crate metadata references. Notebooks can be viewed in the portal, and run in an ATAP BinderHub/JupyterHub workspace. For more details about the architecture and technologies of the portal, see the [Language Data Commons of Australia \(LDA\) architecture document](#).

(From a [working document](#) - What is ATAP?)

The laboratory metaphor in “Community Data Lab” implies a space with a number of instruments and other infrastructure, but also governance and procedures - labs are not simply collections of machines and tools, they have protocols, and practices (such as lab-notebooks) for managing and recording research as a process.

It would be a mistake to take the metaphor too far - the “lab” will not end up being a single service with a single front-door, there will be entry points for various different users, in fact it has become clear in the development of this project that the architecture and approach emerging for the CDL are applicable across the entire [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (HASS and Indigenous RDC) making this in effect an commons-wide integration project.

High level summary: Phases 1 & 2

The following is a high level summary of the work packages, see [Appendix 1: Work Packages](#) for more detail.

Phase 1	Phase 2 - projected
Establish HASS and Indigenous RDC Integration model with “Trove Data Guide” as the centrepiece	Implement FAIR Reuse services generalised “Data guide model” to Data and Analytics guides
Gateway: A Trove data guide (WP-TDG) with recipes for research best practice using the proven GLAM Workbench model	Multiple data guides across the HASS sector
Sustainable Tools pilot: Two key HASS tools integrated with Trove and ATAP and deployed in a flexible, sustainable way (Image annotation and Stylometrics) (WP-SIA and WP-IAW)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More tools deployed in various modes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fixed term services ○ On-demand ephemeral services (notebooks, on-demand servers, APIs) ● Potential: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Supported APIs such as IIIF ○ A FAIR data repository caching Trove and other GLAM data
Data movement and transformations work, including exploring adding International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) support to Trove (WP-DAT)	Continues - based on feedback from Phase 1
NECTAR SERVICE INTEGRATION TO DO	
Integration activities that demonstrate interoperability across the CDL (WP-INT).	Expand learnings from integration work in this project to the broader HASS-RDC and Indigenous Data Network.
Notes	
Open Access data is the main focus, though the Trove data guide will cover some of the complexities of copyright and limits on data use	Will build on ATAP work on data licensing to provide distributed licence-based authorization.

and reuse. Resources that require formal sign-up or approval for licences will not be covered.	
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NOTE: initial planning for this project included a work package for Software discovery. Following discussions with Tom Honeyman, Manager of the ARDC’s [Research Software Program](#), the consulting solution architect, Peter Sefton recommended that this component be withdrawn, pending the development of an ARDC-wide approach to cataloguing software. ARDC is in the process of defining an agenda for research software [\(1\)](#):

Based on the survey’s findings, the report suggests several actions:

- Software infrastructure providers can optimise for general-purpose search engines to make their holdings more discoverable.
- Registries and institutional repositories can be improved on to offer more tailored resources, address the different needs of coders and non-coders, and incorporate the information software searchers value most.
- Researchers, especially those that don’t code, can be assisted to develop their software searching skills and the confidence to evaluate search results.

See: [ARDC Survey Reveals Challenges and Opportunities in Research Software Discovery](#)

Principles

High level principles

This solution architecture is informed by the ARDC Capabilities and Skills Landscape (taxonomy) (2) that outlines skills in Governance, Data, Software and Infrastructure Management capabilities – particularly the Data Capabilities skills (shown in the central part of the diagram below). These skills represent the practices that researchers will need to operate in the CDL environment.

For the purposes of this lab Data Capabilities are the key focus, they are skill sets that need to be fostered in different cohorts; **the team building the HASS and Indigenous RDC to provide and/or map and document the implementation of FAIR data infrastructure that will allow researchers to work with data, and to produce preservable data outputs including code and other analytical products, which in turn will be handed to trusted service providers.** See [Appendix FAIR principles annotated](#) for a discussion of how the FAIR principles are supported by this architecture and the project’s planned work packages.

The most relevant capability to this systems architecture is the FAIR-implementation; the discussion below will show how the lab supports the use of Trove and other data to support Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of data, code and results. Reusability and Preservation depends on being able to **sustain data and services** and this is discussed in sustainability notes for each work package below, and will inform the design of Phase 2.

ARDC Skills Landscape showing which roles are associated with skills. Software engineers are needed to implement FAIR, Data Librarians to maintain and preserve data and metadata and Researchers need skills to operate in the CDL environment.

The above diagram shows which roles are associated with the relevant data management skills. Researchers need to be able to operate in a FAIR CDL environment, with Data Librarians supporting archival repository and discovery services. The team charged with implementing the CDL and the HASS and Indigenous RDC (labelled as Research Software Engineers in the diagram) will design and implement this architecture, that is we will undertake the FAIR implementation.

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A high level view of the research process - with two distinct classes of data, managed long term storage repositories on the right, and workspaces on the left.

The above diagram is a conceptual architectural view of FAIR research data management. In this architecture there is a clear distinction between archival repository services which implement the framework for FAIR data management, providing identifiers, persistence and data discovery and workspaces where users collect, describe and analyse data. Archives and discovery services are shown in the green, right-hand box; these are essential infrastructure for FAIR data. On the left hand side we have ephemeral storage and tooling including on-demand code execution environments such as Binderhub. Together these make up a research environment, which researchers and support staff use to conduct research, archive results etc. Trove belongs firmly in the “repository” side of the diagram but there are some complexities to the mix of metadata and data in Trove, discussed below.

It is important to note that workspaces can be located at a variety of computational sites, from desktop to institutional computing, HPC and cloud computing and tools include desktop and web applications as well as code that runs in a variety of modes; command line, batch HPC, notebooks, and over APIs.

An idealised research data “work-cycle”

This “work-cycle” diagram shows the data creation/acquisition and analysis cycle, with data collected from “instruments” and tools being described and deposited into Archival Repository infrastructure, which offers the persistence and identity services necessary to the application of FAIR. Without repository services it is unreasonable to expect that research teams manage their own data and metadata persistence. The final high-level architecture diagram from the LDaCA project, introduces Standards, and shows how the broad principles of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) need to be implemented in systems and standards. (The standards box reappears below in the section on data publishing with more specific standards related to this project).

Abstract FAIR architecture for standards base archival repositories

Design principles for sustainability

The following principles have been used in designing the CDL solution. The overriding concern is sustainability. Sustainability planning does not only mean having a story about how a particular service will be maintained over time, with assumptions that users will flock to a service and future funding will be forthcoming (though that may, of course be a goal), sustainability means planning for as many eventualities as possible. It is important to recognize that services may be obsoleted by disappearing

funding, lack of interest or the advent of new technologies, but according to FAIR principles data collected still needs to be findable and data reusable, so whatever the fate of a service there needs to be a provenance trail to support published results (R1.2 in the [FAIR principles \(2\)](#)).

Building a sustainable service means ensuring:

1. Above all, that data of all types (inputs, outputs and code) are well described and can be re-homed as cheaply as possible if necessary.
2. Plans are in place for decommissioning services - e.g. if funds are not available to support a long running service.
3. Services are built for redeployment as cheaply as possible - strategies to assist with this include:
 - a. supporting/gateway websites using a mainstream static-site generation mechanism so they can easily be re-worked and re-homed
 - b. Server code is described with all requirements and can be containerized using Docker or similar enabling redeployment on-demand.
 - c. Likewise, for notebooks or other analyses all dependencies are listed with code to support re-use in an environment such as Binderhub.
4. For archival repositories, data should be stored-in and described-by a set of well-documented standards, and where possible should be archived to maximise re-usability, for example by storing data on disk or object storage with its metadata.
5. Where possible, code that supports a particular kind of analysis is available at several levels:
 - a. As a software library (or least a discrete block of code) that implements an analytical method
 - b. As a notebook or command line script that illustrates the method with sample (preferably real) data
 - c. Potentially with a user-interface for non-technical users (but not at the expense of being able to reproduce results
6. Code should be open source by default to support reuse (if only to reproduce results) - if cannot, a case needs to be made for how results can be validated in the future.

Issues- linked data stuff like IIIF requires persistent URIs

Background: Existing Trove Architecture

Trove is a complex service, underpinned by a very complex technology stack - it contains some archival repository services as well as metadata harvested from multiple sources, and has an API which was designed to aid in discovery of resources, but not specifically to support the FAIR principles; the emphasis is firmly on Findability and Accessibility.

Trove [system overview](#)

The Trove data diagram above shows that there are three content repositories under National Library of Australia (NLA)’s management; (1) the web archive, (2) Newspapers and Gazettes and (3) the “Trove Digital Library”. All of these are accessible via Trove but do not have separate services for access - although the Annotations store is actually NLA-managed content as well.

The following diagram re-organized the view of Trove to show which parts of it are repository-like.

Trove architecture showing repository vs index

Trove architecture showing repository components vs index components

The Trove API has two main issues for FAIR research:

- Versioning / stability of data: searches and data downloads are not guaranteed to return the same thing over time as data is added and corrected.
- The distributed architecture with content harvested from multiple sources means that fetching data resources may require tweaking for different sources.

Potential future architecture circa 2025

While the data and metadata in Trove represents a hugely important national asset, some engineering work and user training is needed to make it FAIR-research ready. This section looks briefly at a potential high-level architecture that could be achieved by mid 2025.

This includes ideas proposed so far for the Community Data Lab that will help address the 'FAIRification' of Trove including:

1. Creating APIs and/or proxies that sit in front of Trove, to provide missing functionality such as an IIIF interface, an idea that is championed by Conal Tuohy who has made substantial contributions to the architecture. Exploring the usefulness and sustainability of proxy APIs is part of WP-DAT. These proxies must follow the Trove API terms and conditions and the (planned) NLA/ARDC MOU on research use which will provide guidelines on saving/caching of data.

- Building tooling for researchers to create stable, versioned DOI-referenceable datasets that have been downloaded from the Trove (or other) API so that analytical workflows can be re-run, this is in-scope for Phase 1 - see WP-IAW, WP-SIA, WP-TDG which will all trial this approach for small datasets.

NOTE: This approach is only appropriate for moderately sized Open Access data up to the Zenodo limit of 50GB - it cannot be used for data that is distributed under non-open licences (even click-through licence agreements are problematic). Our expectation is that a Memorandum of Understanding between the NLA and ARDC will support this use case, and will provide advice for researchers on how to label datasets that are static dumps of Trove metadata and data and indicate where more up to date content can be found.

- Creating versioned “data dumps” of substantial parts of Trove, such as snapshots of the entire Newspaper collection, or major subsets thereof, against which repeatable research analyses can be run: the standards-based archive and repository service being used by ATAP and LDaCA has been proposed as a solution here. There is precedent for this as similar dumps were provided to the Alveo project. This is out of scope for phase 1 and would require agreement with the NLA.

The following is a sketch of what the ARDC Community Data Lab could become over time, effectively acting as an integration layer for the HASS and Indigenous RDC as a whole.

One key entry point to the service is a series of data guides that will explain to users how to work with various data sources. In Phase 1, the centrepiece work package is the Trove Data Guide.

Future HASS Community Data Lab Architecture Data and research guides

Future HASS Community Data Lab Architecture: Data and research guides

The next diagram expands the architecture to show both workspace and repository services. The ‘Data Repository and Indices’ box shows both research data repositories (with Zenodo as an example of a general purpose public repository) and ATAP as an example of the research-focused collection, while Trove represents a major data collection that does not have all the features needed for a FAIR-enabled repository. Supplementing Trove is a potential service labelled as ‘HASS Repo’. If implemented, this would store data used by HASS researchers for provenance and integrity purposes (subject to an agreement being reached between the ARDC and NLA about saving metadata from the Trove API research). This has not been scoped in detail but could be included in Phase 2 if a business case can be made and funded for ongoing maintenance of the service.

Potential Future HASS Community Data Lab Architecture

This diagram shows how the first use case above may be supported - with researchers able to create copies of Trove data which are clearly labelled as snapshots for research purposes, stored in a “HASS

Research Data Repository” with clear directions to the Trove API as the source of the data (and more current data).

FAIRification of Trove and other GLAM repositories

FAIRification of Trove and other GLAM repositories via deposit of packaged data

Architecture and Project Methodology

This project needs to be conducted very quickly, so a number of contractors have been asked to contribute in their areas of expertise - this means that the applications chosen to be featured in the first phase of this project have been chosen because they are low risk and are not necessarily representative of all of the latent or potential demand for data-lab services. It will be important as the project moves into Phase 2 to make sure that this approach does not continue; there is a risk that the project could be driven by the technological and/or commercial interests of the contractors (including the author of this document) rather than by researcher-needs.

Phase 1 architecture - implementing FAIR

In this section the phase 1 architecture is presented in terms of the board FAIR principles, starting with Findability.

Findability / discovery of data and tools

The core aid to discovery, and the central point of the CDL will be the “Trove Data Guide” (WP-TDG) led by Tim Sheratt, which will provide a guide-book to using Trove data for research. Note that this is not the only way that researchers may find their way to the CDL environment, but is of central importance. Other entry points include following the provenance links provided with research publications, via links to analytical methods shown alongside code – these are discussed below.

Each of the tools in the data set will be discoverable via the guide, as well as harvestable into a software registry, for example based on the ATAP/Arkisto architecture, or a stand-alone software registry such as the Research Software Directory which is under consideration by the ARDC. Tools may be described in a number of places (or remain un-described) including on the project pages for their git repositories, in public repositories such as Zotero or in guides such as the Trove Data Guide. In phase 1 of this project we will focus on making the tools we are developing indexable although building the indexes for discovery (such as integrating with a potential Research Software Directory, or some other discovery mechanism) may not occur until Phase 2.

High level architecture of the Trove Data Guide (WP-TDG)

High level architecture of the Trove Data Guide (WP-TDG)

The above diagram shows the core components and relationships of the Trove Data Guide, the diagram below depicts how an instance of a code notebook can be instantiated; the running instance then talks to the Trove API.

Launching software tools from Trove Data Guide (WP-TDG)

Launching software tools such as notebooks from the Trove Data Guide

The Trove Data Guide is a low risk project which builds on the [GLAM workbench](#). Its design is inherently sustainable and reusable in that it will consist of open access and open source components that are highly Interoperable across hosts, and not tied to any particular service.

While the data guide offers a skills development approach to introducing research tools to researchers, another avenue will be search services that make data findable. The Australian Text Analytics Platform (ATAP) project has been developing methods for indexing GLAM Workbench-style research code alongside data resources.

The following screenshot shows how notebooks or other tools can be catalogued alongside collections in a repository portal - with a “works with” link.. At the moment these notebooks have minimal metadata - but more detailed metadata will be added, to provide a full citation, and links to example data sets via “works with”-links that can be used to launch a tool which loads the data collection in question.

ATAP Screenshot showing data and code indexing

Trove Data Guide and Findability of software

Trove Data Guide and Findability of software

The diagram above shows the relationship between the ATAP DATA repository and code stored in a git service such as github - with metadata descriptions.

Sustainability notes

This approach:

- builds on the GLAM workbench which has proven to be sustainable without external funding
- Is sustainable via the use of open content, public infrastructure from both the public and private sectors, with minimal reliance on specific service offerings.

The following are elaborated below

- Reuse: showing how the products of running a notebook and notebooks themselves can be packaged in a standard format and published.

Accessibility – making data useable by non programmers

The research applications work package, led by Systemik Solutions will host two applications which serve as pilot applications for repeatable deployment and make data Accessible to non programmers. These will be developed as hosted solutions with a fixed term of support (initially the life of the CDL).

These two work packages (WP-SIA and WP-IAW) are two research applications which are expected to have broad appeal to researchers, but which have as noted above been chosen for pragmatic reasons as they are low risk projects which are in reach for the contractors; they should be seen as exemplars and pilots for a plethora of similar tools in the future.

The Image Annotation Workbench (IAW) is a new tool which is Standards based while Intelligent Archive (IA): Legacy tool which works on standardised (TEI-encoded) text, but is not currently equipped with APIs.

Conal Tuohy will lead the implementation of a pilot IIIF proxy for Trove, under WP-DAT as well as exploring data transformation and movement across the CDL.

Initial deployment of IAW and IA as fixed-term services

Initial deployment of IAW and IA as fixed-term services

Sustainability notes

- Niche and legacy services such as the IA and tools such as the IAW running as hosted applications pose a sustainability challenge. To implement the FAIR principles, outputs of analysis should be published with as much provenance as possible to allow the results to be reproduced from the same data in the future. This leads to the next discussion point: FAIR Reuse.
- Identifiers need to be permanent with plans in place to ensure that they resolve to data (or to an explanation of what happened to it).

Reuse

Reuse of code and services

The (Stylometry) Intelligent Archive is an excellent example of the challenges of keeping software relevant and accessible. Initially developed as a desktop application, it is now also offered as an online service.

There are several ways that code such as this can be run in a modern research computing environment - all of which will be discussed during Phase 1, trialled in the Integration, Data Migration and Transformation work-package if time permits and leading up to planning for phase 2. The highlighted methods in the below table are considered in scope for the WP-SIA and WP-IAW.

Mode	Users	Issues . notes
Desktop	Single	Installing applications on desktop computers is becoming increasingly problematic as IT departments and operating systems become more security focussed and users are less and less likely to have full general purpose computing
Virtualised Desktop	Single	By removing the need to install software locally the tool can more easily be deployed, but getting data in and out of the virtual machine and persisting results may require further development to prevent researchers from losing work in an ephemeral environment.
Fixed Term Hosted online service	Multiple	This is considered the “normal” way of hosting applications, though the fact that hosting cannot be infinitely extended is usually not discussed. By describing this mode as “Fixed Term” we are signalling that planning for the demise of services needs to be done at the time they are offered - for example the next lines in this table look at approaches that could be used once a service’s term has expired.
On-demand medium-term server on demand	Single Multiple	Provisioning a server (similar to the row above) with a web UI using a similar approach to standing up a notebook in BinderHub. This has the advantage that applications do not need to be substantially changed, but there is effort required to craft operational scripts for deployment and deal with user account management etc.
Decompose into APIs and/or libraries	Multiple	This is a stretch goal for WP-SIA - exposing the under-pinning analytical methods of a service so that they can be accessed

in other code such as notebooks. If code is organised for this class of use, it can more easily be packaged for re-use.

Reuse of data products

Publishing analytical results is another important part of the applications-based work packages, WP-IAW and WP-SIA. WP-IAW will pilot the publication of Image Annotations as Research Object Crates (RO-Crates) with the IIIF Annotation, linking back to Trove or other resources.

Initial deployment of IAW publication of results & code

Initial deployment of IAW publication of results

The same pattern of data deposit will be tested and repeated across other parts of the CDL project, with deposit of:

- The results of Jupyter Notebook runs
- Results of Stylometric analyses in WP-SIA (both in hosted and API mode)
- Depositing annotations to public data repositories (there is a suggestion in the report that lead to this work that the CDL could “Provide a Write API [in Trove] for annotations” – given the current status of Trove this is unrealistic, but is achievable using standard research infrastructure.

Sustainability Notes

- The approach of using an API proxy to add IIF support presents a major sustainability challenge – this would need to be hosted and maintained in the long term.

Appendix 1: Work Packages

Phase 1

The following table shows the planned work packages - and an indicative set of starting “backlog” items for each. These will be prioritised dynamically during this project to maximise the impact and interoperability of the growing data lab.

Code WP-	Package	Inclusions / backlog
NSI	Nectar Service Integration (ARDC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Binderhub support for Nectar 2. Hosting for IA and IAW (installation in WP-SIA and WP-IAW – Systemik) 3. Explore and evaluate long-term service requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Virtual desktop deployment of IA and other HASS tools building on Neurodesk (VDI) ● Binderhub style Server on demand (using IA) with preloaded data ● Test installation of ATAP-style data archive and portal/API with harvested tool metadata to provide a directory ● Supporting proxies and caches in front of Trove ● Support CILogon logon, building on current integration activity (see this eResearch presentation from LDaCA) 4. Host GLAM workbench services currently running on private funding. These are simple Python apps, eg: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Trove API Console ● PDF proxy for Zotero ● Trove newspaper places
TDG	Trove Data Guide & Tools catalogue (Sherratt)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trove Guide (Jupyter book) (More info) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide an entry point for researchers

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Detailed documentation of Trove data to support critical understanding of what is, and isn't, in Trove and the sorts of research questions it supports ● Collection of pathways to show how Trove data can be analysed and visualised using existing tools ● Links to other tools and services being developed as part of the project ● Can be extended to include other GLAM data sources in the future <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Enhance metadata on existing notebooks and tools 3. RO-Crate packaging tool for Trove API data
SIA	Stylometrics tool (Intelligent Archive) (Systemik)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IA API, 2. IA platform established on ARDC server, 3. IA site established on ARDC server, 4. Pilot Trove & ATAP collection(s) established, 5. Export of analysis results as RO-Crate (to Zenodo) 6. Skills transfer undertaken to workshop participants.
MAP	Proto-Spatio-temporal Data Guide – first step. Hot spot analysis	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Notebook 1: GHAP WS API: search and filter features of Gazetteer of Historical Australian Places (GHAP) using the WS API. This will illustrate how the basic and advanced search options of the GHAP UI can be accessed through API queries, such as: basic search, fuzzy vs exact match, ANPS and/or contributed layers, bounding box, feature type, LGA, list of placenames. 2. Notebook 2: Hotspot analysis spatial file as input and by calculating distances among points highlights regions of intensity, and provides a measure of how intense that 'hotspot' is. For example, in a spatial file of earthquakes it could differentiate and show you regions where there are more earthquakes. This work will add a temporal dimension. This will be crucial to supporting the mapping the Frontier Wars across Australia with quantitative evidence

		Includes export to RO-Crate of spatio-temporal data.
IAW	Image Annotation Workbench (Systemik)	<p>Approach The proposed approach for establishing requirements includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • facilitation of process to expose researcher requirements of IA API, • documentation of requirements. <p>The proposed approach for the establishment and implementation of IA includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • design and develop IA API, • design and develop results export • design and develop ATAP integration • design and develop IA process and procedure documentation, • develop IA web site, • establishment and configuration of platform and site, • facilitate pilot Trove and ATAP collection(s), • deliver training workshop. <p>Outcomes The outcomes for the GHAP Infrastructure project include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IA API, • IA platform established on ARDC server, • IA site established on ARDC server, • Pilot Trove collection(s) established, • Skills transfer undertaken to workshop participants.
DAT	Data transformation and movement – supporting the integration of tools and data (Tuohy)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trove Interfaces – consider best implementation path for these (as a proxy, code library etc) : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IIIF Proxy for NLA and harvested sites PILOT (dependency for WP-IAW) • In browser Trove API client • Other formats if there is demand (TEI, CSV, RDF, OAI-PMH, ATOM etc) 2. Data movement (pilot / test and report) Torrents / test ATAP Authorised API

		<p>3. Explore the use of https://robustlinks.mementoweb.org/ or similar to allow researchers to archive web content</p>
INT	Integration activities (ALL)	<p>Give priority to integration scenarios that demonstrate value and validate the architecture. This work package can be augmented as opportunities present themselves</p> <p>For example:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. With WP-SIA: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Store Hugh Craig’s TEI XML Plays in ATAP and demonstrate automatically (a) loading them into the IA server (b) using notebooks to perform analysis a la ATAP. b. Ditto with suitable Trove data - possibly via a TEI transform (WP-DAT) 2. RO-Crate deposit to (a) new github repo (b) Zenodo – for GLAM workbench, IA and IAW (integrate with WP-TDG, WP-SIA, WP-IAW) 3. Document data and metadata formats (TEI and other XML, CSV, etc) and their applications to research processes (I/O, analytics, archiving, publishing) 4. Integration spatio-temporal hotspot analysis with Trove queries used to create spatio-temporal datasets.
ENG	Engagement and Skills Development (ARDC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Grants to researchers for workshops - eg Hugh Craig to promote WP-SIA 2. IDEA: Notebook / tool bounty (? Cash rewards for new tooling following a hackathon? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Australian Historical Association conference is July 2023, might be good timing for a workshop. https://web-eur.cvent.com/event/f99aac02-b195-46e5-b1d9-bf5183aea6fc/summary b. A Zotero translator bounty for GLAM collections would help a lot of HASS researchers and help deal with this problem: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Z

		<p style="text-align: right;"> b_e9ZazP4zs-K8ZcbaTCnv6cO_OgmUx4A7U4MFyOFE/edit?usp=sharing </p> <p>3. User support</p>
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Appendix 2: FAIR implementation

This section discusses the implementation of the FAIR data principles [\(2\)](#) in the context of the CDL lab architecture. While, in principle, an individual, cohort or institution *COULD* implement FAIR from first principles, the reality is that FAIR support requires a broad range of services and standards to be in place, such as global identifier schemes, metadata standards and vocabularies, data interchange protocols etc.

To be Findable:

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

Commentary:

- F1 requires that researchers are able to use ID infrastructure such as DOIs and hand-over management of data and ID persistence to an institution. There is now infrastructure in place for researchers to do this for datasets and code that they produce themselves, but up-stream data sources such as Trove do NOT have FAIR-ready services such as versions. (See WP-CAR for details of a potential Phase 2 development)
- F2-3 require that there are appropriate standards available for describing data – building on the demonstrated success of the RO-Crate specification, which brings together several mainstream standards and approaches phase 1 will test the assumption that RO-Crate can serve as an interchange format between source repositories (eg Trove and the GLAM resources is aggregates), workspaces and archival repositories (eg Zenodo, Figshare and institutional research data repositories where they exist).

To be Accessible:

- A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol
- A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
- A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

- A2 requires archival research data repository services to be in place – we will assume that current ARDC advice to use Zenodo and institutional data repositories is prudent, but work may be needed to preserve metadata (and data) from GLAM institutions which may be at risk. NOTE that the Trove API currently does not support this as caching or saving metadata is expressly forbidden.

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:

- R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
- R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence
- R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
- R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

References and Links

1. ARDC Survey Reveals Challenges and Opportunities in Research Software Discovery | ARDC [Internet]. <https://ardc.edu.au/>. 2022 [cited 2022 Dec 18]. Available from: <https://ardc.edu.au/article/ardc-survey-reveals-challenges-and-opportunities-in-research-software-discovery/>
2. Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, et al. [The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship](#). Sci Data. 2016 Mar 15;3:160018.
3. [GLAM Possible uses or integrations of GLAM Workbench in Community Data Lab](#). Tim Sherratt.

Acronyms and Abbreviations

ARDC - Australian Research Data Commons

ATAP - Australian Text Analytics Platform

CDL - ARDC Community Data Lab (formerly known as HASS Community Data Lab and HDCL)

FAIR - findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable

GLAM - galleries, libraries, archives and museums

HASS - humanities, arts and social sciences

HASS and Indigenous RDC - Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons

HPC - high performance computing

IA - Intelligent Archive

IAW - Image Annotation Workbench

IIF - International Image Interoperability Framework

LDaCA - Language Data Commons of Australia

NLA - National Library of Australia

WP - work package